

STUDENT ID: 19B0218

LECTURER: DR. ROZIE

MODULE: BB-2208 HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

DUE DATE: 11TH NOVEMBER 2020

THE STANDARD CAUSAL OF HRM

MADGrow Tech

Abstract/Executive Summary:

MADGrow Tech was established by Wan Muhammad Syazwan Bin Haji Hijazi(Wanzzy Hijazi) in February 2017 and officially launched on July 2017 at the Ground Floor of Ministry of Primary Resources and Tourism by the Minister, Yang Berhormat Dato Seri Setia Awang Haji Ali Bin Apong to provide methods and technologies ,sought to improve farming in everyday use with advanced technology and innovation specially with the rise of various farming technologies with which farmers can monitor, maintain, and grow their farms.

Wan Muhammad Syazwan Bin Haji Hijazi is known as Wanzzy, a young entrepreneur with the goal of transforming the agricultural landscape of Brunei graduated with a Diploma in Business from Laksamana College and is an IMCA Approved Subsea Professional. He has been working with McDermott international Incorporated, oil and Energy Company and he is a provider of technology, engineering and construction solutions to the energy industry and confined among the few locals certified as a Freelance Saturation driver, Commercial Air Driver and Driver Medical Technician. His expertise includes diving, offshore drilling and subsea engineering.

Wanzzy introduced 'Farmbot' farming methods to the local market in terms of encouraging the young people, having stigma that agriculture and poverty belong to the lower class, Farmbot (CNC farming machine) was a boon and the parts of 350 FarmBot were first imported from a Californian company on April 2017. It helps in running farming activities efficiently and with less physical efforts. DIY (do-it-yourself) hydroponic boxes, greenhouses, aquaculture ponds were introduced to reduce manual work, providing the sufficient food supply to Brunei's population. MADGrow Tech and the Agriculture and Agrifood department collaborated to produce high quality, fresh organic fruits and vegetables for the masses to satisfy the country's food requirements and to improve the agricultural productivity through the application of modern farming technologies.

Wanzzy flashes light that people are adamant to see technology with suspicion and they are more concerned about the outcome and he wanted them to be more quality oriented instead of quantity.

Government helped the company by providing an office space to initiate their ideas and implementation for their strategies, Wanzzy suggested opening a springboard hub to influence young agripreneurs towards their passion and business plans to take shape.

Wanzzy's motivation words, three choices everyone has in life, to give up, give in or give it all.

Business Strategy: Business strategy is mentioned as below:

1.To promote technology development in agriculture:

To promote technology development in agriculture MADGrow Tech ensures focus on innovation specially with the rise of various farming technologies with which farmers are now able to monitor, maintain, and grow their farms whether at the comfort of their own home in hopes of transforming ways to aid the government in providing sufficient food supply to Brunei's increasing population and to help themselves in increasing of paddy yield and meet national rice sustainability target.

2.Re-invent modern farming and introduce "Farmbot" to the public:

Most effective strategy was to go through technology, gave existence to the FarmBot into local agriculture, CNC farming machine from a California-based company that helps run farming activities efficiently and with very little physical work. Californian firm provided all software, hardware, electronics and tools required to assemble the machine in Brunei

3.Promote urban farming using recycled materials:

Overall strategic propositions were to promote the urban farming and encourage the use of second hand and used materials to enhance more productivity and recycling pattern and utilization of the goods.

4.Raise awareness in the importance of preserving Brunei's forests:

Raising awareness among the people of Brunei was also a strategic plan to preserve the Brunei's forests.

5. Develop better and improved aquaponic and hydroponics systems:

It was an strategic plan to provide Tech offers DIY(do-it-yourself) hydroponic boxes, greenhouses, aquaculture ponds and the Farmbot system for the consumer market, catering individuals who want to grow plants at home for self-consumption with prices ranging from as low as \$40. This smart box includes everything that require to grow crops at home, minimum input and automatic grow of plants without any intervention.

HR Strategy and Practices: The methodology of HR was used in this context was as below:

1. To provide farming technology solutions:

MADGrow Tech's strategy was to provide the latest farming technologies such as using of Drones not only to speculate the fields but also to disperse the seeds, spraying pesticides and checking soil's thermal conductivity etc. Using the Farmbot system which requires less manual work and with the advanced technology more quality work could be done by making them accessible to the wider society. Wanzzy explained that mapping through drone will eliminate resource wastage as identifying whether the land is suitable for the farming or not before clearing and planting. This device is user friendly and a tracker of the progress of the crops, ensuring the best output.

2. Decrease the reliance of importing food:

Due to increased population Brunei's food production is less compare to its consumption but adaption of advanced technology will improve the food production according to the consumption of the mass and this can encourage and reinforce the manpower too by employing more and more people into agriculture. HR's strategy was to bring a balance between the consumption and growing crops.

3. Increase locally-made products:

HR strategy was to enhance the quality and quantity of the products by providing more work to Brunei's people instead of hiring the foreigners for cheap labour and in long term facing consequence of local people getting unemployed.

4. Encourage Bruneians to plant their own food at their home indoors or outdoors:

With latest technology Wanzzy's strategy was to provide people a set up at home in which they could grow their own food and vegetables to fulfil the economic equation of demand VS supply that means if people could grow food at their own home they would less depend on outside sources.

5. Provide technology outsourcing services:

According to that the HR strategy was to provide the DIY (do-it-yourself) systems like hydroponic boxes, greenhouses, aquaculture ponds and fambot system and for that purpose they launched recently a smart grow box system for the consumer market, catering individuals who would like to grow plants at home for self-consumption and surprising element is that the price of each box is as low as \$40. This smart box includes everything that require to grow crops at home, minimum input and plants can be grown automatically without any intervention. Provide mental fabrication, 3D printing services of the product were also in the strategic planning. They have also created a pocket sized 'M5 Stack' device to help them gather the data by which they can check the moisture levels and soil pH value, Mangaing director Wanzzy Hijazi said.

HR Outcomes:

The Key point here is that the organizational strategies were in alignment with the HR strategies, both were focused on increasing the food production and using the advanced technology to produce the good quality and quantity products. HR practices were more focused on the optimum use of man power including hiring and training them for the more production and financial growth.

Wanzzy's statement of using advanced technology for the growth of a nation included the commitment, quality, output and engagement all the aspects of outcomes. By giving employment to the people of Brunei, he inhabited reinforcement towards their work commitments and quality aspect is done by using the latest and advanced technology of Drone, Farm bots etc. Output is based on manpower+ technology, so that point is also justified in the context of MADGrow Tech.

Improved Internal Performance:

The HRM outcomes lead to the Internal performance of any organisation and in Wanzzy's case the internal performance seems more promising with the increased production, innovation and quality among the people and technology. With the most innovated and advanced technology of using devices their production and quality will lead to the financial turnover and profits. Good training is always a key ingredient of better performance and better performance always lead towards the best financial outcomes same happened in the case study of MADGrow, stronger financial performance lead to more investments in HR practices and better HR outcomes.

Improved financial Performance:

MADGrow emerged as a major agrotech player in the Brunei, with the guidance and support from the Agriculture and Agrifood department by enabling the data-enabled agriculture practice-a farming method making use of environment sensors, mobile computing, wireless communications and drone imaging and financial performance is directly linked with the internal performance. If a company's internal performance is up to the mark, indeed it has a strong financial background

Problem Statement: key issues or Complications:

- ***Lack of understanding of People:***

The major hurdle is the approach of people towards the technology with suspicion. They prefer to use the old patterns of technology as in terms of drone, they use it for only inspection or monitoring their farms instead of performing tasks as to check the soil thermal conductivity, disperse seeds, and spraying pesticides. People in Malaysia and China, use this technology but people in Brunei are reluctant to use it in broader perspective.

- ***People are more concerned of outcomes:***

Rather than looking for quality, people prefer to get quickly the outcome. They prefer to hire cheap foreign labor as it is cheaper but if it goes on in long run, people of Brunei won't be able to get a job.

Alternative Solutions: Pros and cons of possible solutions to problems

1. 'Data enabled agriculture practise':

Data enabled agriculture practise will have the optimum use of environment sensors, mobile computing, wireless communication and drone imaging and this will further enforce the more productive outcomes.

2. Making people aware about the technology:

Making people more and more aware about the technology and its uses and positive and quality outcomes will help them to make their lives better.

3. Reduction in hiring foreign labours:

Foreign labours can be cheap but they affect a country's people in long run as foreigner may take their positions and they have to struggle later on to get the jobs, reduction of hiring foreign labour is essential so as to provide more employment to own people so in long run no one is left unemployed. Wanzzy's primary focus is the growth of his company, perhaps overall growth of the people working within the company by getting more employment opportunities for the young Bruneians and the goods 100% Bruneian-made.

Recommendations: optimum solution with rationale:

1. Wanzzy's way to boost youth participation in farming:

Most effective way is through technology, gave existence to the FarmBot into local agriculture, CNC farming machine from a California-based company that helps run farming activities efficiently and with very little physical work. Californian firm provided all software, hardware, electronics and tools required to assemble the machine in Brunei.

2. *Government's intervention in Company's set up:*

The Government helped the company to get an office space and retain the support it was lacking. Wanzzy recommends the “full package”- collaboration and assistance and Government not only actively involved but put ideas into execution.

3. *More innovation to take place among youth agripreneurs:*

To address the youth's less participation in agriculture due to preset stigma as it belongs to the lower social class Wanzzy has suggested to open a springboard hub where they can turn up and talk about their passions and propose business plans to potential investors.

4. *A space recommendation to discuss the latest advanced Technology:*

Wanzzy has recommended a space where latest advancements in farming technology can be discussed and make the young agripreneurs aware about that.

Implications that have taken place and improved financial performance:

- ***Upgraded lifestyle:***

Due to the efforts of MADGrow Tech the lifestyle of the Brunei Darussalam's peoples have upgraded and embarking upon a path of growth by using the advance technology and self-reliance in agriculture.

- ***Modern Agriculture Technology and Urban farming:***

Modern Agriculture technology and urban farming will trigger interest among entrepreneurs to venture into and sea farming as a viable way to earn a living

- ***Brunei as an urban farming technology provider:***

This will turn Brunei into one of the providers of urban farming technologies in the region.

- ***High Quality, Fresh organic fruits and vegetables to the mass:***

Ultimate goal is to produce high quality, fresh organic fruits and vegetables for the masses to satisfy the country's food requirements and to improve the agricultural productivity through the application of modern farming technologies.

Conclusion:

The future prospects of MADGrow seems bright with the support and initiatives taken by the Government and wanzzy's innovative ideas altogether of aligning the youth entrepreneurs and technology altogether can bring drastic change in the economy as well as the life style of Brunei's people.

References

Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.

R, G., & Every…, 5. (2020). 5 Human Resources Models Every HR Practitioner Should Know. Retrieved 9 November 2020, from <https://www.digitalhrtech.com/human-resources-models/>